

RELEVANCE STUDYING AND MEMORIZING JAPANESE HIEROGLYPHS BY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the article is to present the results of a study on the memorization of Japanese characters by students in modern conditions of access to the global information space. The idea of the article is to prove that it is important to build Japanese classes in hieroglyphics, combining the methods of memorizing hieroglyphs already developed by teachers, at the same time integrating modern technical achievements into the educational process. The use of computer technologies in education, which in no way replaces, but complements the method of memorizing hieroglyphs, helps in mastering and improving knowledge, and opens up new opportunities. The author considers the concept of "global information space". Modern electronic resources for learning and fixing hieroglyphics, which are presented by groups of educational materials and software, are considered in detail.

Keywords: *hieroglyphs, global information space, Internet resources, students, teaching methods.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

Цель статьи - представить результаты исследования запоминания японских иероглифов учащимися в современных условиях доступа к глобальному информационному пространству. Идея статьи заключается в том, чтобы доказать, что важно строить занятия японского языка по иероглифике, сочетая уже разработанные учителями методы запоминания иероглифов, одновременно интегрируя в учебный процесс современные технические достижения. Использование в обучении компьютерных технологий, которые никоим образом не заменяют, а дополняют метод запоминания иероглифов, помогают в усвоении и совершенствовании знаний, открывают новые возможности. Автор рассматривает понятие «глобальное информационное пространство». Подробно рассмотрены современные электронные ресурсы для изучения и закрепления иероглифов, которые представлены группами учебных материалов и программного обеспечения.

Ключевые слова: *иероглифы, глобальное информационное пространство, интернет-ресурсы, студенты, методика обучения.*

INTRODUCTION

The existing types of writing in the world can be divided into two groups: ideographic (hieroglyphic) writing (for example: Egyptian, Chinese, Japanese hieroglyphs) and phonetic writing (for example: Latin, Cyrillic). Learning kanji is an important part of learning the Japanese language. Teaching hieroglyphics to students from countries with non-hieroglyphic writing requires a special approach. The reason is that hieroglyphs are an ideographic script that differs significantly from their usual phonetic script. The Japanese scientific literature presents the results of studies in which it was found that different hemispheres of the human brain are responsible for the study and use of phonetic and ideographic writing, which also does not contribute to the easy assimilation of hieroglyphs by students from countries with non-hieroglyphic writing.¹

¹ Artemov V. A. Psychology of teaching foreign languages. – M.: Enlightenment, 2019. – 279 p.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The problems of teaching hieroglyphic writing to students of countries with non-hieroglyphic writing can be grouped as follows²:

1. *Problems related to the properties of hieroglyphs.*
2. *Problems of teaching methods for hieroglyphics.*
3. *Problems of perception of hieroglyphs by students.*

Let's list the main problems in groups.

1. *Problems related to the properties of hieroglyphs.*

(1) A large number of hieroglyphs to be learned;

(2) A large number of words made up of hieroglyphs that need to be studied;

(3) The shape of the hieroglyphs is complex;

(4) A large number of types of constituent elements of hieroglyphs;

(5) A large amount of information associated with each hieroglyph (shape, meanings, readings, writing order, hieroglyphic key, etc.);

(6) The connection between the form, meaning and reading of the hieroglyph is not obvious;

(7) Information about the readings of hieroglyphs is ambiguous, a hieroglyph may have several Japanese readings "on" and Japanese readings "kun";

2. *Problems of teaching methods for hieroglyphics*

(8) An unsystematic approach to teaching based on rote memorization is often used;

(9) Often the sequence of taught hieroglyphs is not rational;

(10) The time allocated for learning hieroglyphs is limited;

(11) Information and communication technologies (ICT) (computer, Internet) are not used enough when teaching hieroglyphs;

3. Problems of perception of hieroglyphs by students from countries with non-hieroglyphic writing

(12) Perceive hieroglyphs as unsystematized signs;

(13) Do not know the methods of self-study;

(14) are unaware of the various strategies for learning hieroglyphs;

(15) Having memorized hieroglyphs for a short time, they cannot keep them in long-term memory;

(16) The search for hieroglyphs in the hieroglyphic dictionary causes difficulties.

The solution of the above problems requires the development of new approaches and the use of effective teaching methods and tools. We propose a hierarchical approach to teaching, the use of the mnemonic method and information and communication technologies in teaching.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Japanese character is a compact collection of minimal graphic elements, or strokes. A feature of a hieroglyph is an element that can be written with one stroke of a brush without tearing it off the paper.

Example: 女 → { <, J, - }.

The hieroglyph consists of three lines. At the same time, a hieroglyph is a compact set of minimal semantic elements, i.e., elements that are simpler hieroglyphs or elements of hieroglyphs that have a certain meaning.

Example: 露 = 雨 + 足 + 久 + 口.

² Burtseva E. V., Moskvina O. V. To the question of the style of educational and cognitive activity of students in the process of teaching an oriental language // Bulletin of the Novosibirsk State University. – Series: History, philology. - 2013. - V. 12, No. 4. – p. 154–159.

The hieroglyph is decomposed into four hieroglyphs of a simpler form, each of which has its own meaning, and when combining the meanings of the constituent parts, one can to some extent assume the meaning of the composite hieroglyph³.

To facilitate understanding of the structure of hieroglyphs, remembering their form and correct spelling, it is proposed to conduct training in the following hierarchical order from simple to complex⁴:

- ① Katakana characters and characters
- ② Katakana alphabet
- ③ Single element characters
- ④ Multi-element hieroglyphs.

When moving on to the study of hieroglyphs, it is useful to point out to students the similarity of individual hieroglyphs with katakana characters (工工, 力力, 夕夕, ニニ, 口口), as well as hieroglyphs whose constituent elements coincide with katakana characters (左, 江, 仁, 外, 加, 功, 多, 名, 台, 佐, 伝, 治), in addition, to hieroglyphs that have the same reading “kun” as katakana (千「千」, 部「部」, 三「三」, 女「女」) or reading “he” (力「加」, 夕「多」, ハ「八」, リ「利」). This makes it easier for students to move on to studying hieroglyphs that are more complex in form compared to katakana. Practice has shown that students perceive hieroglyphs more easily, feeling their similarity with already familiar signs of the katakana alphabet.

Students should pay attention to the commonality of the rules for writing signs of the katakana alphabet and hieroglyphs.

General rule: the hieroglyph is written starting from the upper left corner and ending with the lower right corner. The following are rules related to specific groups of characters. In the examples, hieroglyphs and their alphabetic codes are written.⁵

1. Features are written from top to bottom. 三 AAA
2. Features are written from left to right. 川 PBB
3. First, horizontal lines are written, then vertical ones. 十 AB
4. First, folding to the left is written, then folding to the right. PO
5. First, the outer part of the character is written, and then the inner part. 句 PGBHA
6. In hieroglyphs, the inner part of which is enclosed in a frame, first a frame is written without its lower part, then the inner part is entered into it, and after that a lower horizontal line is drawn to close the frame. 回 BHBHAA
7. A dot at the top or top left is always written first. 亦 SAPJLQ
8. A dot at the bottom, top right or inside is written last. ABAAQ
9. The vertical line above or to the left of the horizontal line is written first. 上 BAA
10. If the vertical line is in the center and does not intersect with other lines, or if it rests at the bottom of the horizontal line, it is written first. 山 BEB
11. If a vertical line intersects with other lines and does not rest against a horizontal line below, it is written last. BHAB
12. In hieroglyphs composed of horizontal and vertical lines, the bottom horizontal line is written last. ABAA
13. The horizontal connecting line is written last. 女 KPA
14. The backslash at the top of the character is written first. 禾 PABPO

³ Girich V. L., Chuprina V. N. Global information V. and the problem of access to world information resources [Electronic resource]. – Kyiv, 2017

⁴ Zimnyaya I. A. Psychology of teaching a non-native language. – M.: Rus. yaz., 1989. - 219 p.

⁵ Kochergin I. V. Essays on the methods of teaching the Japanese language. - M.: Ant, 2000. - 153 p.

15. A vertical curved line that intersects or connects with other lines in the construction of a hieroglyph is written last. 也 GBC

16. If the outer part of the hieroglyph half-covers its inner part from below and to the left, then the inner part is written first, and then the outer part, in which the horizontal right-folding line is written last. 道 QLALBHAAAQMO

17. If the outer part of the hieroglyph semi-covers its inner part from three sides: left, bottom and right, then the inner part is written first, and then the outer. 凵 POEB

18. If the inner part of the hieroglyph is enclosed between two edge lines, the inner part is written first, then the left and finally the right part. 小 JLQ

However, there are exceptions to this rule when the inner part is written at the end: 火 SLPO; 卩 LQB.

When determining the order of teaching hieroglyphs, one should proceed from the interests of students. But it is recommended to form groups according to meaning, while giving single-element hieroglyphs first, and then compound multi-element hieroglyphs. When teaching compound hieroglyphs, the elements included in them should be given together for a better understanding by students of the meaning of the compound hieroglyph (Table 1)

Table 1. Examples of groups of hieroglyphs (Vorobieva G.N. Tales of hieroglyphs. Part 1. - Bishkek, 2017.)

Group name	Hieroglyphs	Structural elements to be taught at the same time		Composite hieroglyphs group
		Keys	graphemes	
Numbers	一 二 三 四 五 六 七 八 九 十 百 千 万	一 二 口 儿 十 八 十 白	五 七 九 千 万	三 四 六 百
Size, location	大 小 上 下 中 右 左	大 小 口 工 卜	中	上 下 右 左
Days weeks	日 月 火 水 木 金 土	日 月 火 水 木 金 土		
Person	人 女 男 母 子 口 目 耳 手 足	人 女 力 田 母 子 口 目 耳 手 足		男
Verbs	入 止 立 来 行 見 食 生 言 出	入 止 立 一 米 行 見 食 生 言	出	来
Adjectives	丸 太 甘 赤 辛 青 長 重 高 良	甘 赤 辛 青 長 高	丸 太 重 良	
Subjects	刀 弓 斤 井 斗 矢 皿 車 貝	刀 弓 斤 斗 矢 皿 車 貝	井	
Plants, animals	犬 牛 羊 毛 羽 馬 魚 鳥	犬 牛 羊 毛 羽 馬 魚 鳥		

Application of the scanning method for learning to memorize the form and order of writing hieroglyphs.

The scanning method consists in pronouncing a rhyme to memorize the form and order of writing a hieroglyph, namely, in the order of writing, the names of semantic elements are pronounced; elements that match in shape with the signs of katakana; as well as features of hieroglyphs. When using rhymes, even a hieroglyph of a complex shape can be quickly and

permanently remembered. For example, to memorize the complex character 熊 (bear), you can use the following "chant":

熊

む, つき, ひ, ひ,
とん, とん, とん, とん

(漢字, 片仮名, 書記素)

Application of information and communication technologies (ICT) for teaching hieroglyphs.

With the development of ICT, their use for teaching and mastering hieroglyphs is also developing, but their practical use is still insufficient. We bring to your attention some existing resources.

Using the NJStar program.

The NJStar program has the functions of a text editor and a Japanese-English dictionary (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The main window of the NJStar program

For a set of hieroglyphs, two methods are implemented in it. The first method is based on the use of a table of key elements of hieroglyphs. When you specify with the mouse the key elements that are the components of the desired character, hieroglyphs appear on the upper strip, which contain the specified key characters. By scrolling from these hieroglyphs, the desired one is selected and inserted into the text (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Entering hieroglyphs using the table of key elements

According to the second method, the input of hieroglyphs is carried out by entering their reading in hiragana and subsequent transformation into hieroglyphs.

NJStar includes a Japanese-English dictionary, the latest version of which, freely distributed on the Internet, includes over 6,000 characters and about 100,000 words.

Using the KanjiGold program.

The KanjiGold program is designed to test knowledge of the meanings (in English) and reading Japanese characters (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Testing knowledge of the meanings of Japanese characters in English

To begin with, a group of hieroglyphs (range) is selected. For each hieroglyph, 5 answers are offered (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Testing knowledge of reading Japanese characters Database of 2136 Jo:yo:kanji characters.

We have developed a database of 2136 hieroglyphs of the official list of commonly used hieroglyphs, which includes a file with hieroglyph data and a file with key data. The database can be used to search for characters by their attributes. The file with hieroglyphs contains 2136 hieroglyphs, which have the following attributes (Fig. 5):

- 1) NN - serial number

- 2) 字 kanji (the character itself)
- 3) Character code according to the Unicode system
- 4) NS - number of strokes (number of strokes)
- 5) Radical (key element number)
- 6) Symbolic code (symbolic code of the hieroglyph)
- 7) ABC code (alphabetic character code)
- 8) Reading (one Japanese reading of the character “He”)
- 9) Meaning_English (the meaning of the hieroglyph in English)
- 10) Meaning_Russian (the meaning of the hieroglyph in Russian)

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	NN	字	Unicode	NS	NR	Symbolic code	ABC code	Reading	Meaning_English	Meaning_Russian
2	1	一	4e00	1	1	//1//	/A/	イチ	one;	один;
3	2	右	53f3	5	30	//4/1/30//	/PABHA/	ウ	right;	правый;
4	3	雨	96e8	8	173	//173//	/ABGBQQQ/	ウ	rain;	дождь;
5	4	円	5186	4	13	//13/2/1//	/BGBA/	エン	circle; yen; round;	круглый; пена;
6	5	王	738b	4	96	//96//	/ABAA/	オウ	king; rule; magnate;	король; правит
7	6	音	97f3	9	180	//180//	/SAQLABHA/	オン	sound; noise;	звук; шум;
8	7	下	4e0b	3	1	//1/25//	/ABQ/	カ	below; down; descend	ниже; низ; спус
9	8	火	706b	4	86	//86//	/QLPO/	カ	fire;	огонь;
10	9	花	82b1	7	140	//140/9/21//	/ABBPBPC/	カ	flower;	цветок;
11	10	学	5b66	8	39	//42/14/39//	/QLSFFJA/	ガク	study; learning; scienc	исследование; и
12	11	気	6c17	6	84	//84/4/O//	/PAARPO/	キ	spirit; mind;	дух; ум;

Fig. 5. File with 2136 characters [9]

To search for a character in the table, you need to press 2 “Ctrl + F” keys simultaneously, the “Find and Replace” dialog box will open. In the "Find" window, enter one of the attributes of the hieroglyph, in the example, the character code 140/9/21 is taken. After pressing the “Find next” button, the found attribute is highlighted on the table and in this line (in Fig. 6 - line 10) you can see the desired character and all its attributes.

9	8	火	706b	4	86	//86//	/QLPO/	カ
10	9	花	82b1	7	140	//140/9/21//	/ABBPBPC/	カ
11	10	学	5b66	8	39	//42/14/39//	/QLSFFJA/	ガク
12	11	気	6c17	6	84	//84/4/O//	/PAARPO/	キ
13	12						/PR/	キュウ
14	13						/PBABPO/	キュウ
15	14						/POAABQLA/	キン
16	15	空	7a7a	8	116	//116/48//	/SSFLCABA/	クウ

Fig 6. Search for a character by its attributes

Communicating in the language environment provided by the Internet, students are involved in solving a wide range of meaningful, realistic, interesting and achievable tasks. In addition, students can learn to respond spontaneously and adequately to circumstances, which encourages the creation of original statements, rather than the stereotyped manipulation of language formulas.⁶

⁶ Vorobyov V.M., Vorobyeva G.N. Tales of hieroglyphs. Part 2. - Bishkek, 2017.

As an information system, the Internet offers its users a variety of information and resources. The basic set of services may include:

- email,
- teleconferencing
- videoconferencing
- the possibility of publishing your own information, creating your own home page and placing it on a Web server,
- access to information resources (reference directories, search engines, online conversations).

These resources can be actively used in a Japanese lesson. If we talk about mastering communicative and intercultural competencies by students, then this cannot be done without the practice of communication and the use of Internet resources in a foreign language lesson. For example, the Internet virtual environment allows you to go beyond time and space, providing its users with the opportunity to communicate authentically with real interlocutors on topics that are relevant to both sides.⁷

CONCLUSION

The use of innovative multimedia programs and technologies in the process of studying hieroglyphic material along with “immersion” in the language environment is considered by students as an important factor that determines the efficiency of assimilation and memorization of hieroglyphic material. Along with this, 15.4% of students consider it necessary to take into account national traditions in the process of learning the Japanese language. This indicates that the role of cultural factors in the study of the Japanese language is clearly underestimated by students, and this requires special attention from the teacher, who should pay attention to the national cultural traditions of Japan and show that the assimilation of hieroglyphs is easier if the student knows the history of the formation of Japanese writing and language.

The work of a teacher must necessarily be aimed at exploring the possibilities of the information space in order to create new and improved teaching methods that will help students in learning and memorizing Japanese characters. The use of the Internet technology system in Japanese classes is an effective method of memorizing Japanese characters. However, we must not forget that the Internet is only an auxiliary technical learning tool, and in order to achieve optimal results, it is necessary to correctly integrate its use into the lesson process.

The approach described in this article is based on the systematization and coding of hieroglyphs and their elements, the classification of hieroglyphs by complexity, the hierarchical approach, the structural decomposition of hieroglyphs, the algorithmic principle of their study, the use of information and communication technologies, identification methods and includes:

1. Establishing a rational sequence for studying hieroglyphs, taking into account the principles of "from simple to complex" and modularity.
2. Using the method of mnemonic associations for a better understanding and memorization of hieroglyphs.
3. The use of computer technology to study and test knowledge of hieroglyphs.

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